

Towards a Net Zero Emission Pathway: A CLEWs-based Study of Ghana

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Context

- Chronic energy insecurity with growing electricity demand
- 35 % of national GHG emissions from thermal sources

Research Questions

1. What are the effects of reducing emissions from power plants on Ghana's current power generation mix and water use?
2. Is the introduction of Nuclear energy a feasible source of energy in Ghana's energy production mix?
3. What is the financial outlook of emission reduction and nuclear introduction into the power mix?

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Ghana Reference CLEWs System

Fig 1. Ghana's Reference CLEWs System

CLEWs – Climate, land, energy, water system

Scenarios

Using the CLEWs Model the following scenarios were investigated:

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Assumption
Baseline (BAU)	Reflects current energy situation	Current energy policies and regulations remain unchanged
Emission reduction (EMR)	Cap Gas and Bio related emissions by 20.4% by 2030 Contributing to the 64MT CO_2 eq reduction by 2030	EMR Policies are enforceable and maintained through 2055
Nuclear energy addition (NUC)	Introduce 1 GW of Nuclear in 2030	Investment readily available

Results

Energy Mix and Emissions (BAU vs EMR)

Fig 3: Energy generation from power plants (BAU)

NGS - natural gas, SOL – solar, BIO – Biofuel, PWR- power plant, WAT – water, DEMAGRDSL - Diesel for agriculture

Fig 4: Energy Generation from power plants (EMR)

Fig 5: Annual emissions (BAU)

Fig 6: Annual emissions (EMR)

Results

Energy Mix and Emissions (BAU vs NUC)

Fig 7: Energy generation from power plants (BAU)

Fig 8: Energy generation from power plants (NUC)

Fig 9: Annual emissions (BAU)

Fig 10: Annual emissions (NUC)

Results

Investment Costs (BAU vs EMR vs NUC)

Fig 7. Investment Costs (BAU)

Fig 7. Investment Costs (EMR)

Fig 7. Investment Costs (NUC)

Conclusions and Policy Insights

Conclusion

1. Emission reduction target is feasible with an additional investment of \$30B
2. Nuclear energy introduction significantly reduced emissions, and is \$2.5B cheaper than the baseline of \$53.96B

Policy Insights

1. Emissions reduction-related high capital cost requires diversified financing mechanisms from public-private partnerships, international climate finance, and development bank support
2. Nuclear Regulatory Authority must develop a roadmap for the deployment of Nuclear Energy into Ghana's energy generation mix by 2030

Future Work

1. Analyze sustainable biofuel production limits considering land competition, deforestation risks, emissions and food security implications

THANK YOU